

Galactic Center Newsletter

IAUS405: Traversing the Galactic Center in Space and Time, Brno (<https://gc2026.muni.cz/>)

Vol. XXIX / No. 4

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF: Václav Pavlík — EDITORIAL BOARD: Vladimír Karas, Petra Suková, and Maitrayee Gupta

May 21, 2026

Conference photo from the IAU Symposium 405, in front of the Sgr A* model (credit: Lea Szakszonová)

EDITORIAL: INTERNATIONAL ASTRONOMICAL UNION AND THE CZECH REPUBLIC

By VLADIMÍR KARAS

The Czech astronomical community joined the International Astronomical Union (IAU) as early as 1922: at that time, Czechoslovakia was admitted during the first General Assembly, which took place in Rome just three years after the Union itself was formally constituted. Despite the fact that Czechs and Slovaks split their country after 74 years of co-

existence, astronomers in the two successor states continue to be part of the IAU through their respective National Committees. Currently, there are almost 150 members of the IAU affiliated with Czech institutions and about 50 who adhere to Slovakia.

Two General Assemblies were held in the capital city of Prague: in 1967 and 2006. Both events offered multiple symposia on current topics, which attracted many active participants and provided a great impetus to the progress of astronomy and astrophysics in the region. Not only does professional research benefit from the IAU endorsement, but also the education of future generations in the universities that carry out accredited programs

in astronomy and astrophysics. A whole spectrum of undergraduate and graduate levels is traditionally represented at Masaryk University in Brno (Faculty of Science) – the host of the current Symposium, Charles University in Prague (Faculty of Mathematics and Physics), and the Silesian University in Opava (Institute of Physics). Together with non-university research institutes of the Czech Academy of Sciences, all aspects of the Czech membership are supervised by the Czech National Committee for Astronomy.

The General Assembly 2006 stays in the memory of many as the decision moment when the notion of planet was redefined; as a result of the vote, Pluto was removed from

the list, and more rigorous criteria for the fast-growing research on exoplanets were established. It is worth noting that this General Assembly included two events directly relevant to our present meeting: Symposium #235 “Galaxy Evolution across the Hubble Time” and #238 “From Stars to Galaxies – Across the Range of Masses”, which provided ample time to explore connections between black holes and galaxies, including Sagittarius A* supermassive black hole. In that era, new exciting results in the highest-

precision determination of stellar orbits were reported. The proceedings from the Symposia were published by Cambridge University Press. By reading them today, we are reminded about the progress achieved during the recent two decades in technology as well as theoretical fronts. Moreover, they also help us to rephrase the pressing questions that remain unanswered to date.

Just as important as the professional research is the continued and diverse public outreach associated with IAU activities. As-

tronomy dissemination has a lasting tradition in the Czech Republic through the dense network of public observatories and planetaria, joined under the umbrella of the Czech Astronomical Society. Indeed, it is interesting to note that the impressive history of the Czech Astronomical Society dates back to 1917, before the birth of the IAU. ■

THE COSMIC GARDEN: DECODING GREEN PEA GALAXIES IN BRNO

By MAITRAYEE GUPTA

While the universe is populated by grand spiral and elliptical structures, some of its most significant secrets are held by diminutive, vibrant outliers known as Green Pea galaxies. First identified in 2007 by citizen scientists, these compact, low-mass systems appear as luminous green dots in deep-sky surveys. This distinct colouration is not just the result of starlight alone, but rather an intense, narrow-line emission from oxygen gas, ionized by a massive population of exceptionally hot, young stars.

These galaxies serve as local “laboratories” for the early universe. Despite their small size, Green Peas exhibit star-formation densities that are significantly higher than those found in larger, mature galaxies. They are considered local analogues to the high-redshift galaxies that existed shortly after the Big Bang, providing a rare opportunity to study the processes that drove the Epoch of Reionization.

From Genetics to Galactic Evolution

The choice of Brno for this conference offers a profound historical parallel: it was here that Mendel established the fundamental laws of how genetic traits are inherited using pea plants [1]. Similarly, Green Pea

galaxies may be the low-redshift counterparts of early, low-mass dwarf galaxies, and may have inherited similar traits that can reveal the causes behind the primary drivers of cosmic reionization.

By analysing the specific traits of these galaxies, such as their chemical abundance and the escape fraction of ionizing radiation, astrophysicists can reconstruct the evolutionary history of the cosmos. Just as Mendel

looked at the humble pea to explain the complexity of life, we look to these compact green systems to understand the fundamental transformation of the early universe from an opaque, neutral state to the transparent, ionized expanse we inhabit today. ■

- [1] M. Gupta. *Galactic Center Newsletter* **29.2** (2026), 1.
- [2] C. Cardamone et al. *MNRAS* **399.3** (2009), 1191–1205.

A mosaic of 80 Green Pea galaxies taken from the original study [2]. The images are from the SDSS DR7 Explorer pages and have not been sized or re-shaped. The galaxies were imaged originally by SDSS between 2000 and 2004.

ALMA is a revolutionary astronomical telescope, comprising an array of 66 giant antennas observing millimetre and submillimetre wavelengths. It is situated on the Chajnantor Plateau, at an altitude of 5000 m in the Chilean Andes. (credit: Y. Beletsky/ESO)

HOW ALMA DECODES THE VIOLENT PHYSICS OF THE GALACTIC CENTER

By ABHIJEET BORKAR

The Centre of the Milky Way is a bustling metropolis, with a supermassive black hole at its very heart. It is an extreme environment, full of intense radiation and strong gravitational potential, surrounded by a vast amount of gas. The interstellar dust obscures the central region, blocking our view in visible light. There are a few windows of the electromagnetic spectrum that allow us to peer through the veil. The Atacama Large Millimetre/submillimetre Array (ALMA), operating in the high-frequency radio band, offers a unique view of the Galactic Centre (GC), letting us explore phenomena not accessible to other telescopes. In particular, ALMA is ideal for measuring gas and molecules, and has been used extensively with many successes.

Cold Gas and Hot Winds

Milky Way's supermassive black hole, designated Sgr A*, is not very active, but it does have regular snacks. The material for this likely comes from the circumnuclear disk of cold molecular gas. ALMA observations have found clumps of dense molecular gas falling towards the centre at speeds greater than 200 km/s, to eventually feed the black hole. This feeding has its own reaction, known as feedback. The intense radiation

and the turbulent accretion produce hot outflowing winds and jets that push away the surrounding material. Deep, high-resolution ALMA maps of the central region have found a massive, conical clearing in the cold molecular gas surrounding Sgr A*. This clearing stretches outwards for at least 1 pc with a wide 45-degree opening angle, likely as a result of a powerful wind of hot plasma driven by Sgr A*.

Cosmic Chemistry

The molecular gas is not only in the centre but is found hundreds of parsecs out. The Central Molecular Zone (CMZ) is a region of massive, dense molecular gas spanning almost 200 pc, shaped by the intense radiation, turbulence, and gravitational effects. It is a unique laboratory giving us a view into the complex physical and chemical processes in galactic nuclei.

The large program ACES – the ALMA CMZ Exploration Survey – was designed specifically to explore the intricate processes with unprecedented detail, and to address fundamental open questions in star formation and galaxy formation/evolution. The survey has led to the largest ALMA image to date, stitched together from hundreds of observations. It revealed the presence of an intricate filamentary structure of cold molecular gas, shaped by turbulence, shockwaves, and magnetic shearing, spanning sub-parsec to tens of parsecs in size. The physical conditions of the gas along the filaments control the growth of stars and the flow of gas towards the central nucleus.

ALMA has detected dozens of complex molecules in the CMZ, from simple carbon monoxide to many organic molecules like ethanol, propanols, and cyanides, a complex factory of branched carbon molecules, heavy alcohols, and peptide precursors. These molecules act as cosmic instruments for tracing the physical conditions in the GC, help decipher the history of our galaxy, and provide clues for the study of the origin of life in the Universe.

Star formation under extreme conditions

The harsh conditions in the GC, from the strong tidal forces and intense radiation from the supermassive black hole, are detrimental to the formation of stars. The tidal forces should be strong enough to rip apart the gas clouds before they can form stars. But surrounding Sgr A* are a bunch of young stars, which are too young to have been formed far away and migrated to the centre, suggesting that these must have been formed *in situ*. This has been termed the Paradox of Youth.

ALMA observations have revealed the presence of several low-mass proto-stars in the central parsec region, very close to the black hole. Computational simulations have supported the idea that not only can the supermassive black hole allow for stars to form, it may even assist in star formation. Even in the extreme conditions, it is possible for the dense core of the gas clouds to form stars.

The Czech Node of the EU-ARC

The ALMA Observatory has a support network in all three participating regions, called

the ALMA Regional Centres (ARCs), providing support for ALMA users. The European ARC, led by the European Southern Observatory (ESO), has a geographically distributed hub-and-spoke model designed to maximize the scientific return for European astronomers. Within this system, the Czech

node of the European ARC serves a crucial role as the support centre for astronomers in Central and Eastern Europe. Hosted at the Astronomical Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences in Ondřejov, the Czech node is a highly distinct, specialized asset in the network: it hosts the unique, leading expertise

in solar physics with ALMA, actively spearheading the development of special solar observing modes and data processing software. Along with this, it provides support for galactic and extragalactic observations, data analysis, and archive exploration. ■

WHAT HAPPENED TO MONDAY (TUESDAY & WEDNESDAY)¹

By VÁCLAV PAVLÍK

The IAU Symposium 405 opened on Monday with a strong focus on Sgr A*, from horizon-scale physics to its larger-scale environment. On Tuesday, it expanded towards stellar dynamics, star formation, and the structure of the central parsec. Wednesday connected some of the most diverse themes of the conference so far, ranging from stellar dynamics near Sgr A* to cosmic rays, dark matter, gravitational waves, and very-high-energy gamma-ray astronomy.

Monday

The introductory talk was delivered by the Nobel Prize Laureate, Andrea Ghez, and the whole scientific programme then quickly converged on one central theme: high-precision observations of the Galactic Centre. Several talks highlighted how the combination of GRAVITY at the Very Large Telescope Interferometer (VLTI) and the Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) is transforming the field. We can now test general relativistic effects [e.g. 1], and imaging and polarization measurements can now constrain the magnetic structure of the accretion flow around our supermassive black hole [2, 3].

Moreover, our observations are resolving the dynamics of Sgr A* in both space and time. This was reflected in efforts to reconstruct its time-variable structure (effectively “movies” of the emission region). Several speakers also discussed infrared observations using the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) and X-ray observations with

Chandra [4, 5, 6], which are now opening an additional spectral window onto flare physics and particle cooling processes.

Attention also turned to the larger-scale environment of Sgr A*. High-resolution observations are beginning to trace cold molecular gas inflow down to sub-parsec scales [7].

Tuesday

In the second day of the Symposium, we continued discussing the properties of Sgr A*. This includes its dynamics, variability, flare physics, limits on electric charge, or hot-spot models [8].

Several speakers showed that stellar collisions and close encounters may explain the observations of stripped red giant stars [9] or some of the peculiar objects, e.g. X7 [10] or IRS 9 [11].

Then the focus shifted towards the central parsec. Collisions on a much larger scale, involving infalling star clusters, may explain the growth of the Nuclear Star Cluster as well as the supermassive black hole in its core [12, 13].

The GRAVITY+ Collaboration presented their results on the upper limit of dark mass distribution (e.g. in the form of stellar-mass black holes) in the vicinity of Sgr A* [14]. And several other speakers touched on the ‘paradox of youth’, i.e. one of the central unresolved questions, how did young stars appear in the Galactic Centre if they cannot form in such an extreme tidal environment?

Wednesday

We spent the whole day in the central parsec, where several talks focused on the stellar and dusty environment around Sgr A*. One particularly exciting result was the discovery

of the star S301 [e.g. 15], whose orbit may become one of the best future probes for testing the spin of Sgr A*. Other contributions explored hidden populations of stellar-mass and intermediate-mass black holes [16, 17].

Part of the day was also dedicated to multi-messenger astrophysics. Results from the Large High Altitude Air Shower Observatory (LHAASO) collaboration and studies of PeV cosmic rays and particle acceleration near black holes highlighted the Galactic Centre as a natural laboratory for extreme high-energy phenomena [18, 19]. Gravitational-wave astrophysics also entered the discussion through studies of extreme mass-ratio inspirals and turbulent accretion discs [20, 21].

During lunch break, participants also took a conference photo (see the front page). In the afternoon, the scientific programme concluded with a sightseeing tour in Brno, followed by an evening concert at the Brno Observatory and Planetarium. This was perhaps the most diverse conference day yet. ■

- [1] T. Do et al. *Science* **365**.6454 (2019), 664–668.
- [2] A. Ricarte et al. *ApJ* **987**.2, (2025), 152.
- [3] M. Wielgus et al. *A&A* **682**, (2024), A97.
- [4] Z. Summers et al. *arXiv e-prints*, (2026), arXiv:2605.13962.
- [5] S. D. von Fellenberg et al. *ApJ* **979**.1, (2025), L20.
- [6] J. M. Michail et al. *ApJ* **997**.2, (2026), 282.
- [7] M. D. Gorski and L. Murchikova. *ApJ* **995**.2, (2025), L51.
- [8] M. Dovčiak et al. *MNRAS* **384**.1 (2008), 361–369.
- [9] M. Zajaček et al. *ApJ* **903**.2, (2020), 140.
- [10] F. Peißker et al. *A&A* **704**, (2025), A7.
- [11] M. W. Hosek Jr. et al. *ApJ* **999**.2, (2026), L34.
- [12] A. Mastrobuono-Battisti et al. *A&A* **693**, (2025), A22.
- [13] A. Mastrobuono-Battisti et al. *MNRAS* **521**.4 (2023), 6089–6104.
- [14] Gravity Collaboration et al. *A&A* **692**, (2024), A242.
- [15] GRAVITY Collaboration et al. *A&A* **645**, (2021), A127.
- [16] V. Pavlík et al. *A&A* **692**, (2024), A104.
- [17] M. Labaj et al. *A&A* **702**, (2025), A233.
- [18] G. di Sciacio and Lhaaso Collaboration. *Nuclear and Particle Physics Proceedings* **279-281** (2016), 166–173.
- [19] Z. Cao et al. *arXiv e-prints*, (2025), arXiv:2510.06786.
- [20] S. Mitra et al. *MNRAS* **516**.4 (2022), 5092–5109.
- [21] S. Mitra and S. Das. *ApJ* **971**.1, (2024), 28.

¹A deliberate reference to the 2017 film *What Happened to Monday*. After three days of Galactic Centre physics, the distinction between Monday, Tuesday, and Wednesday became increasingly difficult to maintain.